

FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN THE FORMATION OF INFORMATION AND MEDIA CULTURE IN YOUNG PEOPLE

Rakhimova Shakhnoza Anvarovna

Associate Professor, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Sociological Sciences,
Tashkent University of Information Technologies
named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14835477>

Nowadays, the development of information technology is determined by its increasing impact on the life and activities of individuals, society, and the state. The information field, that is, an information complex, a system consisting of information and information gathering and distribution tools, is undoubtedly an important network that manages and directs social relations. In the context of changes in the methods of working with information and the expansion of the fields of application of new information technologies, the influence of information and psychological threats on the individual's mind is increasing.

The competition in obtaining and delivering information, forming an influential public opinion has also become fierce, and has accelerated the exchange of cultures in the process of informationalization of the society. Development of information culture and formation of it in every person in modern conditions is one of the urgent issues.

Recently, there is a growing tendency to look at the concept of information culture as a whole, as a situation of integration of information and culture components of a person. Information culture is considered as an edge of universal culture. Information culture is a systematized set of knowledge, skills and abilities that ensure the effective organization of personal information activities, aimed at meeting the needs of a person for information arising in the course of education, scientific knowledge, independent education, recreation and other activities.

Information culture today requires a person to acquire new competence, including the skills of organizing information-communication dialogue, interaction with the information environment, and the use of adaptive social technologies.

Information culture is the ability to work with information for a purpose, as well as the ability to use information, analyze and transfer computer information technology, new technical tools and methods. The main features of traditional information culture are: information search; information sorting; information analysis; application of information.

Information culture is the purposeful work with information, the formal acquisition of information, processing it using scientific methods, timely transmission, and having the skills and abilities to use modern tools and methods. The importance of information culture in modern society lies in the fact that its formation opens wide opportunities for the relevance of self-awareness of a person, as well as for the development of cultural potential, self-education and interpersonal communication.

Currently, the level of information society is one of the main criteria for assessing the level of development of the state and the most important factor of its economic and political potential. One of the priority areas of informationalization of the society is the formation of the information culture of the individual.

A number of documents published in this regard testify: International Information Summit (Geneva, 2003; Tunis, 2005) In 2006, an open forum of UNESCO was held at the IFLA 72nd World Library and Information Congress in Seoul, and a number of other important directions were held at this forum. At the same time, it was recognized that the issue of forming the culture of receiving information is one of the important directions, and the ideas of its development were put forward. The ideas of IFLA and UNESCO on the formation of information culture have been recognized and approved by the world community.

Also, in 2019-2024, the concept of development of the information library industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the program of measures for the development of the industry, and the organizational structure of the National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi - information resource center were approved.

Creating opportunities to use information as a way of independent education and expanding the scope of communication, providing users with access to quality information resources in any media (print, multimedia and digital), including the Internet, creating and constantly replenishing their own information resources to provide readers with traditional the transition from the service method to providing them with modern information-library services and the development and modernization of remote information-library services to the population was determined as the main task.

Today, in most countries, the development of media and information literacy, media education, information culture of a person is carried out in the directions of regulatory-legal, organizational-technical and spiritual-

psychological education. They serve the effectiveness of the mechanisms of creating conditions for the formation and development of the information culture of the individual, group, community and society in the information society.

The experiences of the leading countries in the field, the United States of America (USA), Canada, Australia, France and Finland, were studied in order to determine the priorities for the introduction of the media competence approach in the development of the information culture of the individual in Uzbekistan.

The US experience of introducing the media competence approach in the development of the information culture of the person.

Currently, in countries such as European countries, the USA, Australia and Russia, media education is included in the education system as a compulsory subject. As early as the 1980s, more than 90,000 people in the U.S. were busy gathering news for television, radio, newspapers, and magazines, the invention of cable networks provided 24-hour uninterrupted news coverage, while more than 1,650 local newspapers reported 7,500 news stories a week.

The expansion of mass media created conditions for the development of media education. Today, in all 50 states, media literacy and media literacy are taught in conjunction with English and the arts. In 30 states, media education is used in the social studies, history and civil rights, environmental and medical sciences groups.

In modern practice, the possibilities of the Internet system are widely used during the teaching of media education in the USA. The Internet also serves educational purposes because teenagers use the Internet to communicate, search for information about their interests, "try on" new social roles, and express themselves.

In the late 90s, one of the most important achievements of the media education movement in Canada was the creation of an Internet resource called the Media Awareness Network, which is still the leader in terms of content, materials, curricula and lesson plans. America's most influential and linked media education sites can be divided into two main groups: media education center, association, and foundation sites, and educational sites with online copies of television channels, newspapers, and magazines.

We can highlight the website of the Center for Media Literacy (www.medialit.org), which is the largest distributor of mass media in the United States. The site provides ideas on how to integrate media education into school

subjects by subject and age group, access to an archive of articles on media education, links to other resources, and other useful information.

The Newspaper in Education Association is still dealing with the issues of integrating printed media into the educational process, methodological support in planning activities can be found on its website www.nieonline.com. Founded in 2000, the Alliance for a Media Literate America (AMLA - <http://www.amlainfo.org>) website is the unique newsletter of the American school of media education, which publishes media education research and results. In addition, this site provides information about events, seminars, conferences that have taken place and are planned for the future.

The Media Education Foundation (<https://www.mediaed.org>), America's leading source of video resources for media education, was founded in 1991. It is a non-profit organization engaged in the production and distribution of video films that form a critical perspective on the media and the social, political and cultural consequences of the media.

Teacher Source (www.pbs.org/teachersource) and Teacher Line (www.pbs.org/teacherline) have online professional development courses for school teachers on their sites, while Adult Learning Service has its own partnership program with colleges. PBS does not produce its own programming, but receives cultural, educational, historical, scientific, sociopolitical, nature programs and news from public television stations and independent sources. TeacherSource's media-based educational materials for teachers are primarily focused on Language Arts. It describes in detail the characteristics and components of the media, the methods of persuasion used in mass media, as well as how media texts are created, interpretation and analysis of various forms of media texts.

The Canadian experience of introducing the media competence approach in the development of the information culture of the person.

In the 90s of the 20th century, media education became a mandatory, permanent component, a component of general education (grades 1 to 12) in all secondary schools in Canada and Australia. In recent years, Canada has been recognized as a world leader in media education.

Canada is home to the famous media theorist Marshall McLuhan. It was he who developed the first special training course on the study of media culture in the 50s. Media culture has become an integral component of the English school curriculum. At the modern stage, the integration of media education is carried out not only in English/French, but also in history, mathematics, health,

technology and similar academic subjects. Courses on media culture are also taught at leading Canadian universities such as York University, Universite de Montreal, Canadian Center for Advanced Film Studies Windfields.

Canadian media pedagogy is based on eight basic principles: 1. All media is the result of product-oriented design. 2. Media creates reality. 3. Listeners evaluate the importance of media texts based on their experience, age, nationality and other aspects. 4. Media has commercial purposes. 5. Media contains a certain ideology and promotes certain values. 6. Media has socio-political importance. 7. In the media, form and content are closely related. 8. Each form of media has a unique aesthetic form.

In Canada, positive results in the field of media pedagogy have been achieved due to the established cooperation between public educational institutions and representatives of various mass media. For the development of the field of media education, significant financial support is provided not only by the government, but also by commercial structures that partially finance various media projects. In general, all scientific and educational centers in the field of media pedagogy in Canada are divided into two main categories: media education organizations belong to the first category, and leading media corporations in Canada belong to the second category.

The Australian experience of introducing the media competence approach in the development of the information culture of the person. In Australia, which is geographically separated from the developed countries of the West, the direction of media education originated in connection with the famous model of G. Lasswell ("communicator" - "information" - "channel" - "receiver" - "influence").

Media education is taught as a compulsory subject in school curricula (grades 1 to 12). In Australia, media educators are united in the ATOM (Australian Teachers of Media) association, which publishes the magazine METRO every three months. ATOM (Australian Teachers of Media) Association regularly holds media conferences, publishes books, and audio-visual training manuals. In Australia, there is no formal curriculum for media education in the primary grades, but it is taught as part of the English language curriculum.

Media training sessions are conducted by teachers who have improved their skills in special courses. Thanks to the development of the Internet in Australia, media education is becoming more and more widespread today, and specialists in this field are becoming leaders at the international level. Media education also has a leading position in the country's universities. An important

direction of activity of research and educational centers in the field of Australian media pedagogy is the integration of media into the main and additional subjects in the school curriculum, development of media education of schoolchildren and youth. Teacher training is mainly carried out in special training courses.

The French experience of introducing the media competence approach in the development of the information culture of the person. The National Audiovisual Institute (L'I.N.A. - L'Institut National de l'Audiovisuel), established in 1947, played an important role in the development of French media education. Its innovative department has created a research collection of audiovisual materials, media publications (mainly television and radio).

One of the prominent projects in the field of media education in France is the Press Week at School (Semainede la Presse dans l'ecole), which has been held since 1976. The project includes not only print media, but also audio and television. Press Week envisages cooperation between students and professional journalists. The goal is to explain the features of media activity to students. This is done through "learning by doing". In this, imitative creative tasks are given and media texts of different genres and forms are created. 7000 French schools participate in the press week.

CLEMI (Centre de liaison de l'enseignement et des médias d'information) is involved in the introduction of media into the educational process, conducting courses for teachers, publishing newspapers, magazines and books devoted to the issue of media education, collecting resources devoted to the problems of media culture. CLEMI implements programs in cooperation with UNESCO.

The Finnish experience of introducing the media competence approach in the development of the information culture of the person. In Finland, media education was included in the curricula of secondary schools from 1970, and from 1977 in higher education institutions. In the 1990s, media literacy in the country was replaced by the concept of media education. The use of media is an important part of the leisure time of young people, especially students. In Finland, youth community centers are well established and are staffed by highly qualified professionals.

Young people can easily visit these centers during working hours, usually in the evenings and on weekends. They come to the centers to interact and participate in various activities. Information resources and youth centers at the libraries of higher educational institutions are an important platform for communication and discussions between adults and young people.

A monthly web magazine called Painovirhe is published. Teenagers write articles, make photo and video products for each issue of the magazine. The web magazine features reviews of various concerts, books and albums, articles on teenage life, poems, stories, video productions and news about the activities of the local youth council.

In general, on the basis of summarizing the learned foreign experiences on the introduction of the media competence approach in the development of the information culture of the person, it was determined that it is necessary to combine information, computer, ICT, and media tools at the modern stage in order to form and develop the information culture of the person. In addition, formation of media competence of a person is carried out through media education. For the development of this field, it was determined that regulatory, organizational, and moral-educational directions play a key role.

In conclusion, it can be noted that today there are a number of problems in the information sector, and there are many cases of gross violation of the privacy rights of citizens, information about their personal life from social networks, technical platforms for the distribution of instant messages, mass information distribution, and messengers. illegal information that affects the physiological and psychological psyche of a person is also distributed.

These problems are covered by the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Principles and Guarantees of Freedom of Information", "On Information", "On Mass Media", "On Protection of Professional Activities of Journalists", "On Protection of Children from Information Harmful to Their Health". requires ensuring the effectiveness of the practice of the rules established by law.

The experiences of the leading countries in the field, the United States of America (USA), Canada, Australia, France and Finland, were studied in order to determine the priorities of the media competence approach in the development of the information culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Their positive experience was analyzed and comments were made regarding the measures planned for the development of regulatory-legal, organizational-technical, moral-educational directions of the media and information sphere in Uzbekistan, and the implementation of media education in the field of education.

References:

1.Медиа ва ахборот саводхонлиги тўғрисидаги Фес Декларацияси (Фес шаҳри, Марокаш, 2011 йил 15–17 июнь).

2.ИФЛАнинг медиа ва ахборот саводхонлиги бўйича тавсиялари (Гаага шаҳри, Нидерландия, 2011 йил 7 декабрь; Россия, 2012 йил 24–28 июнь) ва бошқа хуж.

3. Гендина Н.И. Формирование информационной и медиаграмотности в условиях информационного общества: новая инициатива ЮНЕСКО и проблемы российского информационного образования. // Педагогика. Психология. Выпуск №1 / 2012. – С. 140–161.
4. Очерет Ю. Формирование информационной культуры личности в условиях информационно-библиотечных учреждений. // Информационная культура в контексте новой парадигмы образования: проблемы, поиски, решения. – Кемерово: ОбЛИУУ, 2001. – С. 150.
5. Baran, S. J. (2002). Introduction to Mass Communication. -Boston-New York: McGraw Hill, 535 p.
6. Considine D. (2000). Mastering the Media: The Appalachian Experience. Telemedium. The Journal of Media Literacy, Vol. 46, N 1, pp.22-23.
7. Martineau M. (Ed.) (1988). L'enseignement du cinema et de l'audiovisuel. Paris: CinemAction, 299 p. p.28
8. CLEMI (1996). L'Actualite' et les medias ` a l'ecole primaire, au college et au licee. Paris: CLEMI, 120 p p.16

